

Impact of Yoga on the Reaction Time of School-going Students

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Abstract

Reaction time is a key component of motor fitness and mental performance. Faster reaction time means better alertness, focus, and neuromuscular coordination for school-going children. Improving reaction time can help not only in sports but also in academics and daily activities. Yoga is known to improve both physical and cognitive abilities through regular practice of asanas, breathing exercises, and relaxation techniques. This study aimed to assess the effect of selected yogic practices on the reaction time of children aged 14–16 years. A total of 50 school students were selected and divided equally into two groups: 25 in the experimental group and 25 in the control group. The experimental group underwent a 12-week yogic training program, five days per week, which included Yoga Asanas (like Tad asana, Trikonasana, Vajrasana, Bhujangasana), Surya Namaskar, Pranayama (Anulom-Vilom, Bhramari), and Gayatri mantra. The Nelson Hand Reaction Time Test was used to assess the reaction time before and after the intervention. The control group did not receive any yoga training. Data was analysed using paired and independent t-tests. The results showed a significant reduction in reaction time in the experimental group after the 12-week yoga program ($p < 0.05$), indicating faster response and better neuromuscular coordination. The control group showed no significant change. Regular yogic practices, like asanas, pranayama, Surya Namaskar, and Gayatri mantra, can help improve reaction time in adolescents. This may be because of better mind-body awareness, improved breathing control, and the calming effects of yoga. Yoga can be introduced in school programs as a natural and effective tool for enhancing children's physical and cognitive skills.

Keywords

Yoga, Reaction Time, neuromuscular coordination, quick movement, Gayatri mantra.

Introduction

At the adolescent stage, cognitive processing speed is especially important, as students face competitive academics, sports, and frequent digital use, which may impair attention and coordination (Naik, 2021). Faster reaction time allows quicker understanding, decision-making, and effective responses. School students today face stress, distractions, and less physical activity, which slows their reaction time. Quick responses are vital for learning, sports, and daily life. Yoga, through asanas, pranayama, and meditation, may improve alertness and coordination. Thus, reaction time is not only a psychological measure but also an important indicator of overall mental sharpness and physical readiness in school-going students (Pal et al., 2014).

Reaction time is the duration between the presentation of a stimulus and the initiation of a motor response, reflecting how efficiently the brain processes sensory information and directs the body to act. It involves coordination between sensory organs, the nervous system, and muscles, influencing everyday activities, learning, and sports performance (Shelton et al., 2010). Various factors, including age, practice, fatigue, emotions, and focus, affect reaction time, with physically active and mentally alert students generally responding faster. Reaction time is the speed of responding to a stimulus, such as sound, light, or touch, and is crucial in sports, academics, and daily activities (Magill & Anderson, 2017).

Objective of study

1. To design a yoga training program for school-going students to improve their reaction time.
2. To assess the impact of yogic practices on the reaction time of school-going students.

Review of Literature

Yoga, originating in India, develops mind, body, and spirit (Singhdeo, A. 2025). Patanjali's Yoga Sutras detail asanas, pranayama, and meditation. Beyond spiritual growth, yoga enhances health, concentration, balance, coordination, and alertness. Globally, it supports cognitive skills and responsiveness, benefiting school-going students' learning, sports performance, and daily activities (Telles et al., 2011). Yogic practices such as asanas, pranayama, and relaxation techniques enhance concentration, balance, and nervous system efficiency, supporting quicker responses. Yoga enhances both mental alertness and physical coordination, reducing reaction time (Madanmohan et al., 1992). Loosening exercises and Surya Namaskar prepare muscles and nerves for quick action (Fox et al., 1993; Bhavanani et al., 2013). Asanas like Tadasana and Vrikshasana improve balance, concentration, and neuromuscular coordination (Tran et al., 2021). Pranayama techniques, Chanting the Gayatri Mantra, improve concentration,

reduce reaction time, stabilize the mind, sharpen attention, and enhance cognitive and motor responses.

ॐ भूर्भुवः स्वः। तत्सवितुर्वरेण्यं।

भर्गो देवस्य धीमहि। धियो यो नः प्रचोदयात्॥

Gayatri Mantra chanting, combined with asanas and pranayama, stabilizes the mind, enhances attention, and may reduce reaction time in students. Trataka and Yoga Nidra sharpen the nervous system, enhance focus, and promote relaxation, supporting faster, effective responses (Joshi et al., 1992; Telles et al., 1994; Swathi et al., 2021; Pawlow et al., 2002). Yogic practices offer a holistic approach to improving RT by enhancing both mental clarity and physical responsiveness. Asanas, or physical postures, promote neuromuscular coordination, flexibility, and core strength, all of which are essential for faster physical responses. Studies have shown that regular yoga postures improve physical control and coordination (Devi & Singh, 2014; Pimpale, 2024). Surya Namaskar, a dynamic sequence of twelve postures performed rhythmically with breathing, enhances blood circulation, improves flexibility, and strengthens motor synchronization (Arjun & Sunitha, 2019). It also helps regulate hormonal balance and energy levels, contributing to better responsiveness. Pranayama, the controlled regulation of breath, directly influences the autonomic nervous system. Techniques like Anulom-Vilom and Bhramari improve brain oxygenation, reduce stress, and enhance attention and concentration, leading to improved reaction time (Dilara et al., 2016; Naik, 2021). These breathing techniques calm the mind and improve focus, which are essential for rapid and accurate responses to stimuli (Telles et al., 2013). Mantra Kriyas, such as chanting "Om" or the Gayatri Mantra, promote mindfulness and emotional regulation. Samajdar et al. (2020) found that mantra chanting significantly improved attention span, reduced anxiety, and enhanced mental clarity in young athletes. When the mind is calm and alert, the body responds faster to external cues.

While several studies have explored yoga's effects on flexibility, strength, and coordination, most studies focus on adults or athletes, with few on adolescents aged 14–16. Research often examines single practices rather than integrated programs combining asanas, pranayama, relaxation, and GM chanting. Fewer have focused specifically on its influence on reaction time in adolescents using objective tools like the Nelson Hand Reaction Time Test. Yoga improves mental alertness, concentration, emotional control, and physical coordination. Practices like pranayama, Surya Namaskar, meditation, and Gayatri Mantra chanting reduce stress, enhance focus, and sharpen neuromuscular coordination, affecting reaction time. The long-term effects on reaction time in school students remain unclear, highlighting the need for focused research. This study aims to fill that gap by scientifically evaluating how a 12-week program of selected yogic practices impacts the reaction time of school-going children aged 14–16 years.

Methodology

This study was conducted to find out the impact of yoga on the reaction time of school-going students aged between 14 and 16 years. A total of 50 students were selected randomly from Atharv International School, Aligarh, and divided into two equal groups. The experimental group (n = 25) took part in the yogic intervention, while the control group (n = 25) did not receive any yoga training and continued their routine. The yoga program was carried out for 12 weeks, with sessions held five days a week. Each yoga session lasted 60 minutes, conducted in the morning from 7:30 AM to 8:30 AM.

The yoga programme focused on asanas, pranayama, kriyas, and yoga nidra techniques known to benefit reaction time, which included loosening activities, Surya namaskar, Gayatri mantra, tadasana, Trikonasana, Paschimottanasana, Sarvangasana, Halasana, Chakrasana, Bhujangasana, Shalabhasana, Dhanurasna, Ardha-Chandrasna, Kapalhati, Anulom Vilom brahamari, modified Trataka, and yoga nidra. Shavasana and Makarasana were also performed to provide relaxation between two activities, as suggested by previous literature and yoga experts. All sessions were conducted under the supervision of a qualified yoga instructor.

Reaction time was measured using the standardised Nelson Hand Reaction Time (NHRT) test with a wooden scale before and after the 12-week yoga program. Each student was given ten trials per hand (right and left). From these, the fastest five and the slowest five responses were excluded, and the average of the remaining trials was calculated and recorded both before and after the program. Data were analysed using paired t-tests to examine changes between the experimental and control groups. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant. This approach provided a reliable measure of reaction time performance and helped determine whether the selected yogic practices had a measurable effect on improving the visual reaction time (VRT) of students in the experimental group.

Analysis

A paired sample t-test was applied to investigate the reaction time of the experimental group and the control group subjects.

Table 1: Comparison of the mean between pre- and post-test of the control group of reaction time.

Data	N	Mean	St. Deviation	Error mean	Mean difference	t	p
pre	25	14.72	3.36	0.67	0.39	-.79	0.43
post	25	15.11	2.29	0.46			

(Tabulated t-value=2.064, level of significant=0.05, df=24)

Table 1 shows that the control group did not exhibit any significant change in reaction time from pre-test (M = 14.72) to post-test (M = 15.11). The obtained t value (-0.79) was lower than the tabulated value (2.064, $p > 0.05$), indicating no improvement in reaction time without yoga intervention. The p-value (0.43) was greater than 0.05, further confirming that the difference was statistically non-significant.

Table 2: Comparison of the mean between pre- and post-test of the experiment group of the reaction time.

Data	N	Mean	St. Deviation	Error mean	Mean difference	t	p
pre	25	17.24	3.20	0.64	1.49	2.72	0.012
post	25	15.75	2.65	0.53			

(tabulated t-value=2.064, level of significant=0.05, df=24)

Table 2 shows that the experimental group exhibited a significant improvement in reaction time from pre-test (M = 17.24) to post-test (M = 15.75). The obtained t value (2.72) was higher than the tabulated value (2.064, $p < 0.05$), indicating a meaningful reduction in reaction time after yoga intervention. The p-value (0.012) was less than 0.05, further confirming that the difference was statistically significant.

Graph 1: Significance of the mean difference between pre- and post-test scores of experimental and control groups on Reaction time.

Result and Discussion

The study included 50 school-going students aged 14–16 years. Table 1 shows that the control group had no significant change in reaction time ($t = 0.39$, $p > 0.05$), which means reaction time did not improve naturally. Table 2 shows that the experimental group, which practiced yoga for 12 weeks, had a significant reduction in reaction time ($t = 2.72$, $p = 0.012$), greater than the tabulated value (2.064). These findings suggest that yoga practices effectively enhanced neuromuscular coordination and quick response ability in adolescents. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Findings

The present study was conducted on 50 school-going students aged 14–16 years. Reaction time was assessed using the Nelson Hand Reaction Time test. The control group did not show any significant change in their reaction time across the testing period ($t = 0.39$, $p > 0.05$), indicating that reaction time does not improve naturally without intervention. In contrast, the experimental group, which underwent a structured 12-week yoga intervention, showed a significant reduction in reaction time ($t = 2.72$, $p = 0.012$), which is greater than the tabulated value ($t = 2.064$). This demonstrates that yogic practices contributed to faster neuromuscular responses and improved psychomotor performance in adolescents.

The results of the present study are consistent with many previous studies that show positive effects of yogic practices on reaction time. (Dilara et al., 2016) demonstrated that a single session of Bhramari pranayama can improve reaction time among adolescents, supporting the notion that breathing practices can calm the mind and enhance attention. Similarly, Choudhary et al. (2022) found that a 10-day yoga program led to a significant enhancement in students' reaction time, proving that short-term yoga is also effective. Pimpale (2024) concluded that yoga and pranayama improve human reaction time and coordination, closely matching the result of our longer, 12-week study. (Singh & Singh, 2025) demonstrated the role of yoga in increasing speed in school children, which is directly linked to quicker reaction times. (Samajdar et al., 2020) revealed that chanting the Gayatri Mantra improved attention, memory, and reduced anxiety in young athletes, all of which are factors related to quicker response. This supports our inclusion of mantra kriya in the program.

More evidence is also available from other researchers. (Yadav et al., 2013) reported faster reaction time after yogic breathing and awareness training, suggesting that controlled breathing and focused awareness improve sensory-motor responses. Sudsuang et al. (1991) found reduced cortisol levels and better reaction time after meditation, explaining that stress reduction may be one mechanism behind the result. In the same line, Streeter et al. (2012) explained that yoga increases parasympathetic activity and gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA) levels in the brain, which calms the nervous system and improves response speed. (Naveen & Telles, 2003) also observed faster motor responses in reaction time tasks after yogic breathing. Likewise, Telles et al. (2013) showed that alternate nostril breathing improved attention and accuracy in students, further supporting the role of pranayama in improving psychomotor efficiency.

Other studies have also reported similar improvements in young populations. (Pradhan & Nagendra, 2009) found yoga training improved memory, attention, and psychomotor speed in children, while Hariprasad et al. (2013) demonstrated that yoga enhanced executive functions and reduced anxiety in adolescents, both of which indirectly help in improving reaction time. (Arjun & Sunitha, 2019) stated that yoga improved coordination abilities in high school students, again confirming our findings.

Recent research evidence has highlighted the positive impact of yoga on reaction time. A meta-analysis by Ghuntla and Dholakiya (2023) reported that yogic activities, including asanas, pranayama, and meditation, significantly shortened both auditory and visual reaction time, reflecting enhanced sensory-motor processing. Similarly, Kumbhar, Desai, and Padmaja (2020) observed that regular meditation improved auditory and visual reaction times in medical students, indicating better cognitive control and attention. (Sonwane and Mishra (2016) also found significant improvement in reaction time and physiological efficiency among both normal and hypertensive participants after yoga and pranayama intervention.

Along with yoga postures and breathing techniques, chanting mantras has also been recognized as a powerful tool for enhancing concentration and reducing reaction time. Malhotra et al. (2014) demonstrated that mantra chanting and listening to rhythmic music facilitated faster reaction times by improving focus and minimizing distraction. The Gayatri Mantra, one of the most ancient and revered Vedic chants, is frequently used in yogic practices (Rigveda, Mandala 3.62.10). Its rhythmic recitation –

“Om Bhur Bhuvah Swah, Tat Savitur Varenyam, Bhargo Devasya Dhīmahī, Dhiyo Yo Nah Prachodayāt” – is believed to stabilize the mind, enhance attentional capacity, and improve psychomotor responses (Sivananda, 1934). Through this mechanism, Gayatri Mantra chanting, when combined with asanas and pranayama, may significantly contribute to the reduction of reaction time in school-going students.

Yoga originated in India several thousand years ago, and today it is widely practiced across the world as a means of physical, mental, and spiritual development. It has been proven effective in enhancing overall well-being, reducing stress, and improving cognitive efficiency. The integration of yogic practices such as asanas, pranayama, meditation, and mantra chanting has shown strong influence on neurophysiological functioning, particularly in regulating attention, memory, and reaction time (Sonwane & Mishra, 2016). Reaction time (RT) is defined as the interval between the presentation of a stimulus and the initiation of a motor response, and it is an important indicator of central nervous system efficiency and psychomotor performance. In school-going children, faster reaction time is essential for effective learning, sports participation, and quick decision-making in daily life (Ghuntla & Dholakiya, 2023).

All these studies suggest that yogic practices affect not just the physical body but also the mental state, leading to overall improvements in how quickly a student perceives and reacts to a stimulus. The findings not only validate the positive influence of yoga on improving reaction time but also highlight its potential in fostering mental alertness, quick decision-making, and better neuromuscular coordination. Yoga practices contribute to sharper focus, reduced stress, and enhanced responsiveness, which are essential for the overall development and performance of school-going students.

Conclusion

This study demonstrated that the regular practice of selected yogic exercises, including asanas, Surya Namaskar, pranayama, Gayatri Mantra, and kriya, significantly improved the reaction time of school-going children aged 14–16 years at Atharv International School. After 12 weeks of structured yoga training, the experimental group showed faster responses to visual tests compared to the control group. This improvement may be

attributed to yoga's role in reducing stress, enhancing breathing efficiency, and fostering better concentration. The findings indicate that yoga can serve as a simple and effective approach to support both physical and mental performance in adolescents. Therefore, incorporating yoga into the daily school routine can contribute to the overall development and well-being of students. In view of these findings, it is recommended that schools introduce yoga sessions as part of their regular curriculum and that teachers receive basic training to guide students effectively. At the policy level, yoga can be considered a valuable component of holistic education, promoting not only academic achievement but also mental alertness and psychomotor efficiency. Future studies may further explore these outcomes by including larger samples, female students, different age groups, and extended intervention periods to assess long-term effects. Such research would strengthen the evidence base and widen the application of yoga for enhancing learning, sports participation, and overall health in children and adolescents.

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